

**Survey of the FPCEE-Blanquerna University Research
Evaluation System**

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Introduction and participants

This report presents the findings from the survey conducted among the research staff of FPCEE-Blanquerna. A total of 26 participants responded, representing 13% of the overall research personnel.

Respondents primarily taught in the following academic programs: Psychology (42.3%), Primary Education (23.1%), Early Childhood Education (15.4%), Physical Activity and Sports Sciences (15.4%), and Speech and Language Therapy (3.8%).

In order to better understand how perceptions of the research evaluation system vary across different professional trajectories, the responses were also analysed according to participants' research profiles. This segmentation was based on the EURAXESS framework, which categorises researchers into four stages of their career development:

- R1 – First Stage Researcher: doctoral candidates or equivalent,
- R2 – Recognised Researcher: postdoctoral researchers or equivalent,
- R3 – Established Researcher: researchers with a significant level of independence,
- R4 – Leading Researcher: Senior researchers leading research agendas and teams.

Among the 26 survey respondents, four were classified as R1 (15.38%), two as R2 (7.69%), 10 as R3 (38.46%), and 10 as R4 (38.46%).

The report is structured in two main sections: A descriptive overview of the survey results, including the analysis of responses segmented by participants' research profiles, and a summarising diagram outlining the key findings.

Descriptive Results and Segmented Responses

1. Strengths of the Research Evaluation System

1.1. Most positively valued aspects

Participants identified five main strengths of the research evaluation system: the standardisation of criteria, institutional acknowledgement and follow-up, its formative purpose, the diversification of evaluation criteria, and the support received (Tables 1 and 2).

The most frequently mentioned aspect was the standardisation of criteria, which was praised for 'its clarity and transparency' (pt11). Participants also appreciated the institution's commitment to acknowledging and monitoring research outputs, stating that 'the fact that research itself is evaluated is the best aspect' (pt21). Additionally, the formative purpose of the system was valued, as it was perceived to 'help set goals for researchers' self-assessment' (pt7).

Table 1

Most positively valued aspects of the FPCEE-Blanquerna Research Evaluation System

Most positively valued aspects	n	Explanation
Standardisation of criteria	10	Establishes quantitative, systematic, and transparent criteria.
Acknowledgement and follow-up	6	Reflects institutional acknowledgement and ongoing monitoring of research output.
Formative purpose	4	Supports self-assessment and goal setting through feedback.
Criteria diversification	2	Includes qualitative indicators and recognises activities such as thesis supervision or project leadership.
None	2	Participants indicated there were no positively valued aspects.
Technical support	1	Refers to assistance provided by the Research Office and University Library staff.

Table 2

Most positively valued aspects by career stage

Most positively valued aspects	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Standardisation of criteria	10	1	1	4	4
Acknowledgement and follow-up	6		1	1	4
Formative purpose	4	1	1		2
Criteria diversification	2			2	
None	2	1		1	
Receipt of support	1			1	

2. Weaknesses of the Research Evaluation System

2.1. Most recurrent weaknesses

With regard to the difficulties or limitations they have experienced in the evaluation process, participants bring out the categories: limited diversification of criteria, none, duplication of efforts/bureaucracy, lack of support and resources, competencies, and lack of intermediate monitoring (see Tables 3 and 4).

The most frequently mentioned are the limited diversification of criteria, none, and the lack of support and resources. Regarding the diversification of criteria, participants emphasise the importance given to scientific production, acknowledging its complexity in certain areas. At the same time, other types of publications or dissemination tasks are not highly valued. One participant mentions: ‘Precisely because it is so focused on scientific production, when there are fields in which it is very difficult to publish in journals included in WOS or Scopus (1-2Q) and the most real possibilities are to publish in predatory journals and pay 4,000 euros....’. (pt21)

Regarding the category of lack of support and resources, they note that work overload, difficulties in managing time, and the demands of evaluation have an impact on scientific production. One participant commented: ‘The lack of time means that I am not able to produce as much as I would like, but the evaluation seems to me to be correct, even though it is also very demanding.’ (pt1)

Table 3

Most recurrent weaknesses of the FPCEE-Blanquerna Research Evaluation System

Most recurrent aspects	n	Explanation
Limited diversification of criteria	6	Not adequate assessment of innovation and transferability, but relying too heavily on metrics such as journal quartiles and indicators that are not useful for all disciplines.
None	6	Participants indicated there were no most recurrent weaknesses.
Lacks support and resources	5	Lack of time and financial incentives for research linked to evaluation, especially for those who have extensive management and teaching responsibilities.
Duplication of effort/bureaucracy	4	Bureaucratic burden, completing information repeatedly and adapting it in new formats, such as the CV and navigating through confusing and poorly centralised platforms.
Competencies	2	Difficulties in language skills, such as English, and professional development through

		publications and competitive projects.
Lack of intermediate monitoring	1	Absence of a structured, intermediate self-assessment system to track and reflect on the researcher's progress over time.

Table 4

Most recurrent weaknesses by career stage

Most recurrent aspects	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Limited diversification of criteria	6	2	-	2	2
None	6	-	-	3	3
Duplication of effort/bureaucracy	4	1	-	2	1
Lacks support and resources	5	1	1	3	-
Competences	2	-	-	-	2
Lack of intermediate monitoring	1	-	-	-	1

2.2. Unclear, Outdated, or Unfair Aspects in the Evaluation Process

Regarding unclear, outdated, or unfair aspects of the evaluation system, the participants largely mentioned that there are none. However, some participants mention the limited diversification of criteria and role overlap (see Tables 5 and 6).

Regarding the limited diversification of criteria, as in the previous section, they mention that diverse aspects such as teaching and tutoring, transference, social impact, innovation and other tasks inherent to research are not valued on evaluation, but that priority is given to quantifiable values without taking into account the diversity of areas and complications in publication. One participant mentioned: ‘Yes, there are aspects that are not highly valued, such as the review of scientific articles.’ (pt16)

As for the role overlap category, they again mention that management tasks and teaching dedication are not taken into account in the evaluation, as this hinders scientific publication. One participant mentions that there is limited intermediate monitoring and that although the evaluation aspects are clear, these people are not followed up: ‘On paper, it seems to me to be correct. My impression is that we are not strict enough at the moment of truth in assessing underperformers.’ (pt10)

Table 5

Unclear, outdated or unfair aspects of the FPCEE-Blanquerna Research Evaluation System

Unclear, outdated or unfair aspects	n	Explanation
None	8	Participants indicated there were no unclear, outdated or unfair aspects
Limited diversification of criteria	4	Not adequate assessment of innovation and transferability, but relying too heavily on metrics such as journal quartiles and indicators that are not useful for all disciplines.
Role overlap	3	Overlapping of roles between research, teaching and management, which implies a dedication of time that has repercussions on scientific publication.
Limited interdisciplinary criteria	2	Disparity among disciplines (social sciences, humanities, and health sciences) in evaluation criteria.
Limited intermediate monitoring	1	Absence of a structured, intermediate self-assessment system to track and reflect on the researcher's progress over time.
Low impact	1	Doubts about the real impact of the results on the evaluation system.
Lack of a clear system	1	Lack of explanation in the process of completing the assessment tools
Competences	1	Difficulties following some aspects of the criteria of the appraisal process

Table 6

Unclear, outdated or unfair aspects by career stage

Unclear, outdated or unfair aspects	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
None	8	-	-	5	3
Limited diversification of criteria	4	2	-	1	1
Role overlap	3	-	-	1	2
Limited interdisciplinary criteria	2	-	1	1	-
Lack of intermediate monitoring	1	-	-	-	1
Low impact	1	-	-	1	-
Lack of a clear system	1	-	-	-	1
Competences	1	-	-	1	-

2.3. Relevant Dimensions Overlooked in the Evaluation Process

Several dimensions of research activity that are not being taken into account are mentioned. The most recurrent are the dimensions related to knowledge transfer and the social and economic impact of the projects (Tables 7 and 8).

The participants mention on several occasions that transfer and dissemination are not considered in the evaluation, despite being included in the strategic axes, but not in the criteria for quartiles or scientific journal committees. They also mention that non-competitive projects are not taken into account, but that they do have a high transfer value, generating both social and economic impact as displayed in these two excerpts: ‘These three (transfer, social impact and interdisciplinary work), which are at the core of the strategic plan, are not at the level of quartile criteria, for example, or scientific journal committees, and I think it is contributing a lot to the common project.’ (p9). ‘Yes, especially the participation in non-competitive projects but with a high value in terms of transfer, since they generate a direct and significant impact on the improvement of society.’ (p13)

Table 7

Dimensions not taken into account, of the FPCEE-Blanquerna Research Evaluation System

Dimensions not taken into account	n	Explanation
Transference	14	Knowledge transfer and dissemination are often undervalued in evaluation processes, but their importance and prevalence in academic activities are increasing.
Social and economic impact	10	The consideration and invisibilisation of projects with a high impact on social and economic improvement.
Interdisciplinary work	3	Consideration of networked and cross-disciplinary work
None	3	Participants indicated that no dimensions were not taken into account.
Group-individual tension	2	Not including an assessment of the involvement of individuals in the research group and how the group is progressing. Likewise, not taking into account other roles beyond being PI (e.g., being line managers) or encouraging the selection of new leaders.
review articles	1	The review of scientific articles
Thesis tribunals	1	Involvement in thesis tribunals
national network - third sector	1	Creating a national network
Limited assessment of tutoring of doctoral students	1	Tutoring and supervision of doctoral students in the evaluation process.

Insufficient recognition	1	Low recognition of impactful work outside academia
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Table 8

Unclear, outdated or unfair aspects by career stage

Dimensions not taken into account	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Transference	14	3	-	4	7
Social and economic impact	10	2	-	5	3
Interdisciplinary work	3	-	1	-	-
None	3	-	-	2	1
Group-individual tension	2	-	-	1	1
review articles	1	-	-	1	-
Thesis tribunals	1	-	-	1	-
national network - third sector	1	-	-	1	-
Limited assessment of tutoring of doctoral students	1	-	-	-	1
Insufficient recognition	1	-	-	1	-

3. Opportunities of the evaluation system

3.1. Improvement promotion

On a scale from 1 to 5, participants rated the system's ability to foster individual continuous improvement with an average score of 3.12. In contrast, group-level improvement was rated slightly lower, with an average of 2.88.

In explaining their ratings, participants acknowledged several strengths: the formative purpose of the system (n = 4), standardised criteria (n = 2), and institutional follow-up (n = 1). However, the majority emphasised its limitations, which included a lack of support (n = 9), limited diversification of criteria (n = 5), and tensions between individual and group dynamics (n = 2) (Tables 9, 10 and 11). Furthermore, two participants felt that the system had no real impact on promoting research productivity, or that they were unsure.

Table 9

Limitations affecting individual/group-level promotion of improvement

Limitations in the promotion of improvement	n	Explanation
Lack of support	9	Lack of time and financial incentives for research linked to evaluation, especially for those who have extensive management and teaching responsibilities. Additionally, there is a lack of spaces for interaction and discussion between research groups for strategic research planning.
Limited criteria diversification	5	Not adequate assessment of innovation and transferability but relying too heavily on metrics such as journal quartiles and indicators that are not useful for all disciplines.
Group-individual tension	2	Not including an assessment of the involvement of individuals in the research group and how the group is progressing. Likewise, not taking into account other roles beyond being PI (e.g., being line managers) or encouraging the selection of new leaders.

Table 10

Strengths affecting individual/group-level promotion of improvement by career stage

Strengths in the promotion of improvement	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Formative purpose	4	1	1		2
Standardisation of criteria	2				2
Institutional follow-up	2	1			1

Table 11

Limitations affecting individual/group-level promotion of improvement by career stage

Limitations in the promotion of improvement	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Lack of support	9	1		5	3
Limited criteria diversification	5	2		2	1
Group-individual tension	2		1	1	

3.2. Potential changes or innovations to improve the research evaluation system

Participants proposed a range of ideas aimed at improving the current research evaluation system. These suggestions were organised into nine thematic categories: Responsible and Inclusive Criteria, Efficient and Smart System, Support and Recognition, Qualitative, Flexible and Personalised Evaluation, None, Rigorous and Mandatory Application, Leadership and Teamwork Criteria, Co-Creation of Evaluation Criteria, and Research Collaboration (see Tables 12 and 13).

The two most frequently cited areas for potential innovation were the incorporation of responsible and inclusive criteria and the development of a more efficient and smart evaluation system. As one participant noted: ‘To value, for example, applied research that responds to specific social needs; participation in co-creation initiatives with local or international organisations; or the production of open and accessible materials that facilitate knowledge transfer’. (pt12)

Additionally, the importance of a flexible system that respects the diversity of academic disciplines was emphasised. One respondent highlighted the risk of applying uniform standards across fields: ‘Adapt the research evaluation process to reflect the diversity and reality of all scientific fields within the institution. Research MUST be evaluated, but not through a homogenising approach that penalises certain disciplines’. (pt15)

The need for stronger support and recognition mechanisms was also underscored. Beyond funding and time allocation, participants called for institutional support in creating individualised research plans. As one participant suggested: ‘I propose supporting researchers in developing a personalised research plan to enable more tailored and effective planning’. (pt 23)

Table 12

Potential changes or innovations to improve the research evaluation system

Potential changes or innovations for improving	n	Explanation
Responsible and Inclusive Criteria	6	Incorporation of interdisciplinary approaches, co-created research, open science and inclusion practices. Also includes recognition of applied research with tangible societal impact, such as outreach and dissemination activities that engage citizens.
Efficient and smart system	6	A more automated and integrated evaluation model that is compatible with other systems, streamlining the process.
Support and recognition	5	Offering financial resources, time allocation, and

		tools for personalised research planning, supporting both research-focused and teaching-focused staff.
Qualitative, flexible and personalised	3	A model adapted to researchers' career trajectories that incorporates qualitative aspects of research activity.
None	3	Participants reported having no specific proposals for improvement.
Rigorous and mandatory application	2	Making the evaluation process compulsory and ensuring consistent application of established criteria.
Leadership and teamwork criteria	1	Inclusion of specific criteria that value leadership roles in research groups and lines.
Co-creation of the evaluation criteria	1	Encouraging collective discussion and the development of evaluation criteria among the research community.
Research collaboration	1	Promoting collaboration and resource-sharing among research groups to enhance research activity.

Table 13

Potential changes or innovations to improve the research evaluation system by career stage

Potential changes or innovations for improving	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Responsible and Inclusive Criteria	6	1		4	1
Efficient and smart system	6	1		3	2
Support and recognition	5			2	3
Qualitative, flexible and personalised approach	3	1		1	1
None	3			1	2
Rigorous and mandatory application	2				2
Leadership and teamwork criteria	1		1		
Co-creation of the evaluation criteria	1				1
Research collaboration	1				1

3.3. Good practices

When asked whether they were aware of *good practices* that could be relevant or beneficial for FPCEE-Blanquerna, ten participants suggested various strategies and models. These included:

- Reduction of teaching hours to allow for greater research focus (n = 2),
- The development of shared research plans aimed at collaboratively achieving institutional research goals (n = 2),
- Adoption of European evaluation criteria (n = 1),
- The Australian portfolio-based evaluation model (n = 1),
- The Research Excellence Framework (REF) used in the United Kingdom (n = 1),
- The creation of Research Offices specifically dedicated to managing grant applications and funding calls (n = 1),
- A more efficient, ethical, and qualitative evaluation model (n = 2).

3.4. First step towards improving the current assessment system

To conclude the section on opportunities for the research system, participants were asked to suggest what they considered the first and most essential step towards enhancing the current research evaluation system (see Tables 14 and 15).

The most frequently cited first step was the provision of financial support and time allocation, emphasising the need to create structural conditions that make research a feasible and valued part of academic life. One participant suggested that incentives should be offered not only to support research activity, but also to encourage broader participation: ‘Incentives should be designed for those who receive a positive evaluation in order to motivate others to engage in research as well. Otherwise, even if the evaluation system changes, I’m not sure much transformation will be made’. (pt7)

The second most frequently mentioned first step was the co-creation of the evaluation criteria. Participants highlighted the need for greater participation and representativeness in the development of the evaluation framework. One participant proposed: ‘An ad hoc commission should be created to thoroughly review the current evaluation criteria, and it should be diverse and pluralistic’. (pt3)

Table 14

First step towards improving the current assessment system

First step towards improving the current assessment system	n	Explanation
Financial support and time allocation	8	Provision of financial resources and incentives for those who receive a positive evaluation, as well as time allocation and reduction of teaching load for those subjects evaluated.. Emphasis is placed on recognising research as a core professional responsibility, rather than an optional activity.
Co-creation of the evaluation criteria	4	Establishment of a diverse and inclusive

		commission to develop the new evaluation criteria, ensuring that the process is transparent and shared with the entire research community.
Responsible and Inclusive Criteria	3	Inclusion of innovation, applied research, and knowledge transfer as key elements of evaluation, recognising contributions with social and institutional impact.
Qualitative, flexible and personalised approach	3	Development of a more flexible model tailored to the nature of each discipline, incorporating qualitative components and reasoned, constructive feedback.
Compatibility and transparency	2	Alignment with updated national agencies' criteria through quantifiable and clearly defined standards, minimising ambiguity in evaluation processes.
None	1	Participants reported having no specific proposals for improvement.

Table 15

First step towards improving the current assessment system by career stages

Potential changes or innovations for improving	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Financial support and time allocation	8	1	1	3	3
Co-creation of the evaluation criteria	4	1		1	2
Qualitative, flexible and personalised approach	4	1		2	1
Responsible and Inclusive Criteria	3			2	1
Compatibility and transparency	2			2	
None	1				1

4. Threats or risks of the evaluation system

Participants identified several internal and external factors that could negatively affect the effectiveness of the research evaluation system at FPCEE-Blanquerna (see Table 13). The most frequently mentioned was *External Metric Pressure* (9 mentions), referring to the influence of external evaluation systems that prioritise quantitative metrics such as the number of publications, quartiles, or authorship. Participants expressed concern that this emphasis could shape research agendas and create pressure on researchers, especially when such criteria do not align with the specific context or reality of the institution, as reflected in

the following comment: “they are often very specific and assess quantity, authorship, and quartiles” (pt15).

Regarding internal factors, one of the most frequently mentioned was *Work Overload*, referring to the excessive teaching, administrative, or management responsibilities that limit researchers’ time and motivation to engage in research activities and actively participate in evaluation processes. Some participants also emphasised the need for the evaluation system to adequately recognise the time and effort devoted to management, teaching duties, and, in particular, the supervision of doctoral theses—a task that is often not properly accounted for or sufficiently valued in terms of its workload and the research involvement it entails.

Cultural Practice also emerged as a relevant factor, encompassing beliefs, values, and unwritten norms within the institution that affect how research and evaluation are perceived and may foster resistance or scepticism toward evaluation processes. This is illustrated by one participant’s comment: “Many faculty members wrongly believe that their schedule consists only of teaching hours and consider research optional.” (pt 15).

Another issue, mentioned to a lesser extent, was *Loss of Purpose and Meaning*, where participants viewed evaluation as a bureaucratic formality with little real impact on professional recognition or institutional improvement, leading to disinterest. Lastly, four participants indicated *No Factors Identified*, with responses such as “I wouldn’t know how to answer” or “None.” (see Tables 16 and 17)

Table 16
External and Internal factors in research evaluation

External or internal factors	n	Explanation
External Metric Pressure (EF)	9	Pressure stems from external evaluation systems that prioritise quantitative metrics (number of publications, quartiles, authorship) as primary indicators of research performance.
Work overload (IF)	5	Excessive teaching, administrative or management workload or role overlap reduces the time and motivation of researchers to engage in research activities and participate in evaluation processes.
Cultural practice (IF)	3	Encompasses the beliefs, values, and unwritten norms within the institution that influence how research and evaluation are perceived, as well as active attitudes of resistance, scepticism, or distrust toward evaluation processes

External or internal factors	n	Explanation
		among academic staff.
Loss of purpose and meaning (IF)	2	Evaluation is often perceived as a bureaucratic formality with little to no impact on professional recognition, career development, or institutional improvement, leading to disinterest or a lack of engagement.
No factors identified (NIF)	4	Participants indicate that they don't know how to answer, do not identify any relevant factors or risks, or express a lack of knowledge about the topic.

Table 17

Most recurrent external and Internal factors in research evaluation by career stage

External or internal factors	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
External Metric Pressure (EF)	9	1	1	3	5
Work overload (IF)	5	1	-	4	-
Cultural practice (IF)	3	1	-	1	1
Loss of purpose and meaning (IF)	2	1	-	1	-
No factors identified (NIF)	4	-	-	1	3

Participants identified several perceived risks associated with the current research evaluation system at FPCEE-Blanquerna, including Quantity–Quality Imbalance, Research Activity Decline, Questionable Ethical Standards, Accreditation Misalignment, Talent Drain, Research–Society Transfer Gap, and Worsening of Institutional Prestige, as well as cases where No Perceived Risks were reported (see Table 15).

The most frequently mentioned concern was the *Quantity–Quality Imbalance*, highlighting the risk that the system will continue to prioritise numerical indicators, such as the number of publications or bibliometric impact, over qualitative dimensions of research, such as innovation, social relevance, or methodological rigour. As participants expressed, there is a fear of “.... if evaluation becomes purely metric-driven.

Research Activity Decline refers to researchers withdrawing due to feeling undervalued or abandoning valuable projects that do not fit evaluation metrics, as expressed in “*Less and less research will be done and, when it is done, it will have a limited impact*” (pt 12).

Questionable Ethical Standards remained a significant concern. Participants highlighted that the evaluation system might foster unethical practices or shift focus away from the true mission of research. This includes concerns about practices such as honorary authorship, or the growing trend of paying to publish, as captured in the remark: “*but I am VERY worried about paying to publish*” (pt 10).

Accreditation Misalignment was also noted, referring to the potential consequences of misalignment between the institutional evaluation criteria and national or international standards, which could hinder researchers’ ability to obtain official accreditations or certifications. One participant explicitly pointed out this risk: “*We may lose accreditation opportunities*” (pt 5).

Two participants mentioned the risk of *Talent Drain*, emphasising that skilled researchers might leave the institution for other universities, sectors, or countries, seeking better conditions or recognition.

Another concern raised by two participants was the *Research–Society Transfer Gap*, referring to the persistent disconnect between scientific production and its application or transfer to society, public policy, or educational practice. One participant explained this in detail, highlighting how their entire career had focused on aligning research with teaching in Physical Education didactics, building strong connections with schools, social organisations, and public administration to ensure high-quality teaching and real community impact. However, they mentioned that most of this work is not recognised within the current research evaluation system and warned that, without reform, “*new faculty may limit their community engagement to merely data collection, losing the collaborative intervention link, and teaching may become secondary*” (pt 21).

Worsening of Institutional Prestige was identified by two participants, highlighting the risk that FPCEE-Blanquerna might fall behind other universities and lose its capacity to position itself as a centre of research excellence. Such a scenario could negatively impact the institution’s ability to attract talent or establish strategic collaborations, as implied by concerns about limited research impact and potential deterioration of its institutional image.

Despite these concerns, five participants reported *No Perceived Risks*, responding with statements like “I don’t know” or simply “None” (see Tables 18 and 19).

Table 18

Most recurrent perceived risks in research evaluation

Perceived risks	n	Explanation
Quantity–Quality imbalance	8	Risk that the system will continue to privilege numerical indicators (e.g., number of publications, bibliometric impact) to the detriment of qualitative assessments of research (e.g., innovation, social relevance, methodological quality).
No perceived risks	5	Responses indicate that participants do not perceive any relevant risks, have no opinion, or are unsure about potential consequences if the current research evaluation system remains unchanged.
Research activity decline	5	Research activity diminishes, either because individual researchers withdraw (e.g. demotivation due to feeling undervalued) or because valuable projects and research lines are not pursued (e.g. interesting projects being dropped because they don't fit evaluation metrics, neglect of less visible research areas).
Questionable ethical standards	5	The research evaluation system can foster unethical practices or lead researchers and institutions to lose sight of the true mission of generating meaningful and impactful knowledge.
Accreditation misalignment	3	Misalignment between the institutional research evaluation system and national or international standards hinders researchers' ability to obtain official accreditations or certifications.
Talent drain	2	Skilled researchers leave the institution for other universities, sectors, or countries.
Research–Society transfer gap	2	Persistent gap between scientific production and its application or transfer to society or public policy.
Worsening of the institutional prestige	2	Risk that the institution may fall behind other universities and lose its ability to position itself as a center of research excellence. This affects both its national

Perceived risks	n	Explanation
		and international prestige and its capacity to attract talent, funding, and strategic collaborations.

Table 19

Most recurrent perceived risks in research evaluation by career stage

Perceived risks	N	R1	R2	R3	R4
Quantity–Quality imbalance	8	1	1	4	2
No perceived risks	5	-	-	1	4
Research activity decline	5	1	-	2	2
Questionable ethical standards	5	1	1	2	1
Accreditation misalignment	3	1	-	1	1
Talent drain	2	-	-	2	-
Research–Society transfer gap	2	-	-	2	-
Worsening of the institutional prestige	2	-	-	1	1

Annexes

Survey data: [Qüestionari del Sistema d’Avaluació de la Recerca Universitària FPCEE-Blanquerna \(respostes\) - Fulls de càlcul de Google](#)